
Analytical Study of Abstract and Keywords in the Domain of Library and Information Science Journals

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Introduction:

An abstract is a brief overview of a lengthy work that is usually utilized in professional and educational contexts. Its major goal is to give readers a concise synopsis of a document's key ideas, goals, methods, findings, and conclusions without making them read the whole article.

“The abstract is the part of a research article that is most often read, hence accuracy in the abstract is essential”.(Roy, M Pitkin 1998)

“The article’s abstract serves as one further step in turning the article into an object, for the abstract considers the article as a whole and then makes a representation of it” (Berkenkotter & Huckin, 1995). Well prepared abstract is the image of the article. It represents the original work. Most of the time researchers read abstract and select articles for the review of Literature and sometimes take the decision to read the whole article or it’s not useful for our research.

Specific information is included in the standard abstract format, which comprises the following elements: (1) the study's aim or purpose; (2) a description of

the methods; (3) an explanation of the study subjects (4) a summary of significant findings; and 5) conclusions and implications. The majority of journals have length restrictions on abstracts. The Instructions for Authors contains rules for writing an abstract for a journal article. The standard abstract length is 150 words, which gives ample space to accurately describe the entire article's content while remaining sufficiently concise to just include the most important details.

Guidelines for articles are also provided by the library and information science journals that were chosen for the study, such as the DESIDOC Journal of Library and Information Technology, The Annals of Library and Information Studies and Library Herald. As per the DESIDOC Journal of Library and Information Technology journal concern, the abstract length for research papers mentioned 200 words and for Review articles 150 words.

The Annals of Library and Information Studies journal length of abstract quoted 150 to 200 words. Similarly the Library Herald journals Length of abstract mentioned 300 words.

As per the above parameters researchers think to study to compare the articles abstract mentioned in above journals.

Importance of Abstract in Research Articles:

A research paper's abstract is essential since it fulfils a number of purposes like **Research Summary:** It offers a brief overview of all the major findings, conclusions, methodology, and research questions from the full study. This makes it possible for researchers to rapidly evaluate whether the document is relevant to their interests without having to read the entire text.

Promotes Fast Awareness: Professionals and scholars frequently check abstracts to determine whether reading the entire work is worthwhile. A properly written abstract facilitates their quickly comprehension of the key concepts of the study.

Creates Context: Abstract helps to define the significance of the work by introducing the research challenge and providing an overview of how the study fits into the larger area.

Ability to be discovered: An accurate and concise abstract increases the probability that others will find the similar article. Also research databases and search engines utilize the keywords included in abstracts for indexing works.

Basically, the abstract is essential for drawing in the intended audience and facilitating a wider readership's comprehension of the research.

Review of Literature:

Fain, J. A. (1998) highlighted in his article writing an abstract, that the essential

elements of crafting an effective abstract for scholarly articles, emphasizing clarity, conciseness, and the inclusion of key components such as purpose, methods, results, and conclusions. They stated that for summarising the study maximum 150 words are required in which maximum sentence information is covered. To encourage reading of the full article, improve readership, and make retrieval easier in the future, the abstract should accurately, briefly, effectively, and informatively summarize the content of the article.

Bazerman, Charles (1988) discussed in *Shaping Written Knowledge: The Genre and Activity of the Experimental Article in Science*, investigates the methods used to disseminate scientific knowledge through the experimental papers genre. The book explores the format and style of scientific writing, focusing on the abstract—a vital part of presenting and summarizing research—and its traditions. Bazerman talks on how abstracts serve to summarize the main ideas of scientific research, emphasizing the need to strike a balance between comprehensiveness and brevity. He looks at how study objectives, methods, findings, and implications are effectively communicated in abstracts and how this process reflects larger trends in scientific communication and knowledge generation.

Xiaoli, Ji, (2015) in his article, *Comparison of Abstracts Written by Native Speakers and Second Language Learners* investigates the differences in abstract writing between native English speakers and non-native English speakers. For the comparison they selected two corpus sets. In the first Corpus thirty abstracts authored by native speakers from one international

conference are collected, while thirty abstracts from Chinese researchers from the same conference are included in the second corpus (Corpus B). The tense and structure analysis reveals that the abstracts authored by Chinese researchers vary significantly from those written by native speakers. From a structural point of view, native speakers pay attention to technique and result, while Chinese learners concentrate on introduction and result.

Numerous studies done related to abstract writing. However no such study is still carried out in comparison of abstract published in Library and Information Science Journals.

Objective:

The following are the objectives of the current study.

- 1) To evaluate the length of abstracts in technical writing across journals related to library and information science.
- 2) To determine the length of sentences used in the abstract.
- 3) To determine the length of keywords in technical writing related to library and information science.

Scope:

Comparison of length of Abstract in technical writing journals in the domain of library and information Science. The primary information source for this study are Indian journals on library and information science. When gathering the relevant data, the following three journals published between 2008 and 2012 are taken into consideration. The online version of these

source journals mentioned below are available.

- 1) DESIDOC Journal of Library and Information Technology.
- 2) The Annals of Library and Information Studies and
- 3) Library Herald

Methodology:

A total of 551 articles published in the above mentioned journals were chosen for this study. The length of abstract articles, Length of sentences measured by using online tool i.e. Text analyser Tool. In this tool if we put the abstract of the article, the result shows the number of words in this abstract and no. of sentences of the same.

Additionally, an effort has been made to measure the number of keywords that appear in each published paper across three source journals. The number of sentences in each article were also counted in a similar manner.

In this manner, the necessary data has been gathered, processed, and taken into account with the objectives that have been established.

Hypothesis:

The following hypothesis is considered for the study.

The selected dataset comes from the Library & Information Science source journals, and the article abstract lengths adhere to journal-specific norms.

Data Analysis:

This table 1 presents the number of articles published annually from 2008 to 2012 in three journals: Annals of Library and Information Studies (ALIS), DESIDOC

Journal of Library and Information Technology (DESIDOC), and Library Herald (LH). The total number of articles over the 5-year period, the total number of articles published across the three journals is 551. DESIDOC Journal of Library and Information Technology published the highest number of articles i.e. 260, followed by ALIS (171), and Library Herald i.e. 120. Table 1 also shows that the lowest number of articles were published in the year 2008 i.e. 99 out of 551 articles. However out of 551 articles the highest number of articles

were published in 2009 i.e. 121. Table shows that the DESIDOC Journal of Library and Information Technology journal has been publishing the most articles every year as compared to other two journals. The highest number of articles i.e. 63 published in the year 2012 in DESIDOC Journal of Library and Information Technology. Library Herald had the lowest number of publications, however in comparison overall five years, 2009 had a notable increase with 39 articles were published.

Table 1: Number of Articles Published in the Selected Journals

Sr. No.	Year	No. of Articles Published in			Total
		Annals of Library and Information Studies (ALIS)	DESIDOC Journal of Library and Information Technology	Library Herald	
1	2008	35	49	15	99
2	2009	34	48	39	121
3	2010	40	47	26	113
4	2011	36	53	23	112
5	2012	26	63	17	106
Total		171	260	120	551

Table 2. Year-wise Number of Abstract Published in selected journals

Sr. No.	Year	No. of Abstract Published in			Total
		Annals of Library and Information Studies (ALIS)	DESIDOC Journal of Library and Information Technology	Library Herald	
1	2008	35	49	15	99
2	2009	34	47	19	100
3	2010	40	47	26	113
4	2011	36	53	23	112
5	2012	26	63	17	106
Total		171	259	100	530

In Table 2, the abstracts of articles published in the source journals by year are displayed. The current study examines three periodicals produced in the field of library and information science: the Library Herald, the DESIDOC Journal of Library and *Miss. Pallavi Dhoke & Dr. Milind Anasane*

Information Technology, and the Annals of Library and Information Studies. There were 551 publications published between 2008 and 2012, according to Table 1. Out of these 551 articles 530 articles published abstract. DESIDOC Journal of Library and

Information Technology published 259 abstract out of 260 Journals. Which means in one abstract article not published. In Annals of Library and Information Studies out of 171 articles 171 abstract published and in Library Herald out of 120 articles only 100

articles abstract present. That shows that 20 abstract articles were not published. In 2009 Library Herald 4th issue was devoted to Professor P. N Kaula tribute articles. In this article the abstract is not mentioned.

Table 3: Number of articles determined by abstract length considering the number words

Sr. No.	Range of Words in Abstract	No. of Articles	Percentage	Cumulative No. of Articles	Cumulative Percentage
1	00-50	39	7.07%	39	7.07%
2	51-100	175	31.76%	214	38.83%
3	101-150	186	33.76%	400	72.59%
4	151-200	89	16.15%	489	88.74%
5	201-250	45	8.16%	534	96.91%
6	251-300	11	1.99%	545	98.91%
7	301-350	4	0.72%	549	99.64%
8	351-400	2	0.36%	551	100%
Total		551	100.00%		

In this study, I tried to check the length of abstracts of articles published in source journals by considering their words and it is displayed in Table 3. From Table 1 it shows that a total of 551 articles were published in the selected three journals from 2008 to 2012. Table 3 shows that out of 551 articles, the length of the abstract of 186 articles has ranged between 101 to 150 words. The percentage of which is 33.76 %. The next lowest figure is 175 articles that range between 51 to 100 words. The

percentage is 31.76 %. If we consider that the standard length of the abstract should be 150 to 300 words then 331 (186 + 89+45+11) articles are coming in the range of it. The percentage of it is 60.06 %. From table 3 we observed that 214 articles abstract length is below 150 words however the 6 articles abstract length was exceeding 300 words. It can be stated that 38.83% of articles' abstract length are below 150 words and 1% articles' abstract length are exceeded as per standards..

Table 4: Length of Abstract based on the Number of sentences

Sr. No.	Range of Sentences in Abstract	No. of Articles	Percentage
1	00-00	21	3.81%
2	01-10	470	85.29%
3	11-20	51	9.25%
4	21-30	7	1.27%
5	31-40	2	0.36%
Total		551	100%

The number of articles is distributed according to the range of sentences in their abstracts presented in table no. 5. It can be observed that the highest no. of articles i.e. 470 articles have abstract with 1 to 10 sentences. In percent 85.29 % articles abstract sentences range in 1 to 10 sentences. This shows that authors often write one to

ten phrases in their abstract. Followed by 51 abstract articles, in the range of 11 to 20 sentences. Two articles have an abstract with a 31 to 40 sentence range. This table also observed that an abstract with 0 sentences or no abstract at all is found in 3.81% of the publications. It means that in 21 articles no abstract is found.

Table 5: Number of Articles in terms of Number of Keywords

Sr. No.	Range of Keywords	No. of Articles	Percentage
1	00-00	218	39.56%
2	01-05	238	43.19%
3	06-10	93	16.87%
4	11-15	2	0.36%
Total		551	100%

Keywords are essential words or phrases that sum up a document's or analyses major ideas. They draw attention to important facets of academic writing, it helps in searching the relevant information or articles. Every research article needs keywords as a result. Generally speaking, no other source addresses the optimal number of keywords for a research article. But generally, it should be up to 10 keywords. The DESIDOC Journal of Library and Information Technology Author's Guidelines, among the three source journals, states that authors should include no more than six to ten keywords in their articles. The table 5 presents the distribution of articles based on the range of keywords they contain. In this table we observed 238 articles out of 551 Articles, keywords published in the 01 to 05 range. The percentage of the same is 43.19 %. Similarly, 6 to 10 keywords are found in 93 articles. That is, 16.87% of the total. Very

few articles published keywords in the 11 to 15 range. The percentage of which is 0.36%. During the year 2008 to 2012 a large proportion i. e. 39.56% articles have 0 keywords. It means that in 218 articles have no keywords.

Testing of Hypothesis:

As previously stated, the purpose of this study's first objective is to examine, "the length of abstracts in technical writing published in journals related to library and information science" To that end, the following hypothesis was developed.

The selected dataset comes from the Library & Information Science source journals, and the article abstract lengths adhere to journal-specific norms.

In the study the total 551 articles published in the year 2008 to 2012 were analysed. While analysing the data all three source journals guidelines check and compare with each other.

On the basis of this comparison, the dataset represents article abstract lengths that are impacted by the standards and requirements unique to Library & Information Science (LIS) publications. The lengths of abstracts for articles published in source journals for Library & Information Science between 2008 and 2012 generally follow the 150–300 word range. However, quite a few publications (38.83%) have abstracts that are less than 150 words, indicating inconsistent adherence to accepted standards. Only one percent of abstracts are longer than 300 words.

Conclusion:

In addition to discussing the length of abstracts in technical writing published in source journals, this study looks at other aspects of the source articles, including length of keywords, and counts the sentences of the abstract. The standard length of an abstract is generally 150 to 300 words. However our study shows that the majority of articles nearly 60% have an abstract that is between 150 and 300 words

long. Considering the quantity of sentences in the abstract, the study focussed on 470 articles having a range between one to ten sentences. Concerning keyword count, it is anticipated that this quantity will fall between six to ten words. However, 93 articles out of the 551 in the current analysis had keywords in this range. It basically makes up 16.87% of the total.

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